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Disaster Risk Reduction Management Initiatives of Accommodation in Banaue Ifugao

James C. Lobhoy, MM-BM

Ifugao State University - Main Campus, Nayon, Lamut, Ifugao, Philippines

Corresponding Email Address: lobhoy24@gmail.com

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Abstract.

This study evaluates the disaster preparedness of hotel accommodations in Banaue, Ifugao, a major tourist attraction and a UNESCO World Heritage site vulnerable to natural disasters. The research describes the hazards and risks faced by these hotels, assesses the implementation of existing DRRM policies and procedures, and identifies gaps that need to be addressed to upgrade the disaster risk reduction system. The study used a descriptive-evaluative research design with a self-constructed questionnaire as the primary instrument. The key findings revealed that hotels in Banaue face significant natural hazards, with typhoons being the most prominent (70.1% of respondents) and landslides following (53.7%). The most critical potential risks to hotel operations are power outages (68.5% of respondents) and disruption of water supply (57.4%). The level of DRRM implementation was rated as "sometimes", with an overall weighted mean of 2.92 for preparedness, 2.79 for prevention and mitigation, 4.01 for response, and 3.31 for recovery and rehabilitation. The study concludes that the overall level of DRRM implementation is inconsistent, and most measures are only implemented "sometimes," indicating a lack of standardized and continuous application of DRRM protocols. To strengthen preparedness and resilience, the study recommends focusing on key interventions, with staff training and education being the most frequently identified area for improvement. It is also recommended that hotels implement a certification process to foster a culture of preparedness and resilience.

Keywords: Disaster Risk Reduction and Management (DRRM), hotel accommodations, Banaue, Ifugao, Philippines, disaster preparedness, risk assessment, tourism industry, emergency response